

The hybrid SQL approach to full-text search

Alexander Powell

24 February 2022

E-mail address for correspondence: alexanderp@packt.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6911-1890>

Abstract

Implementing full-text search is generally assumed to require the adoption and configuration of a specialist software product such as Elasticsearch. Experimentation described here indicates that less esoteric approaches are possible. The hybrid SQL approach involves using an indexing script to generate a phrase index that is then loaded into a standard SQL database for querying via a suitable client application. The technique is inexpensive and relatively straightforward, and allows a performant full-text search capability to be implemented with comparative ease.

Keywords:

phrase indexing, SQL database, full-text search, information retrieval

1. Introduction

The ability to search large volumes of text with little effort is something that as consumers of digital information we take more or less for granted, but nonetheless the provision of such capability can be a non-trivial undertaking for publishers. As a fundamental problem in information retrieval [1,2], full-text search is often seen as the sort of computational challenge best devolved to a specialist third-party tool. Online research into the available software options for full-text search typically turns up a rather limited number of products, such as Sphinx, Xapian, Lucene, and Elasticsearch. (Some earlier ‘search standards’ such as OpenText appear to have declined in visibility in recent years, concomitant with their becoming more focused on serving the needs of specific markets¹.) The claim of this paper is that there remains a place for full-text search within the domain of problems we might wish to consider tackling ourselves.

The approach reported here is termed the hybrid SQL approach because it combines a relational SQL database with a separate indexing script. The latter is used to generate a phrase index of the content to be searched, and the phrase index data is then uploaded into the database for querying via a suitable client application. After outlining the indexing process I describe the upload and query processing steps. The paper ends by reflecting on a number of general considerations.

2. Method

Indexing

The Python script that performs the indexing function has been described elsewhere [3], and the reader is referred to that source for additional information. Script variants have been developed

¹ <https://www.opentext.com>

to index both PDF files and (X)HTML files, in whole-corpus and incremental modes. The whole-corpus indexers iterate through a collection of files at a specified folder location, extracting the terms from each file and adding them to a new corpus index. The index is a set of mainly binary files, the formats of which are summarised in **Appendix A**. The incremental indexers are intended to be called from a batch file, and act on just a single specified file. Having extracted terms from the specified file they add them to a pre-existing index.

Once the text has been extracted from a content file, it is split into a series of clauses, a clause being a run of words between punctuation marks. Each clause is split into its component words, and the phrases in the clause are then recognized. Phrases are actually constructed, in a fairly exhaustive manner, by advancing through the clause one word at a time and creating the runs of words that begin at each starting word. For each starting position, word runs – phrases – are generated of progressively increasing length, up to a predetermined limit (usually three or four words) or the end of the clause if that occurs sooner. Only a relatively small fraction of the candidate phrases are indexed, on account of the occurrence of stop words at impermissible locations.

When a phrase is added to the index, a check is carried out to determine whether it has been encountered before in an already-indexed file. Each phrase – meaning here phrase type not phrase token – is represented by a single record in the file *global-phrase-stats.dat* and a single record in the file *phrases.idx*. The latter associates the phrase string with a unique numerical ID, which is used to refer to the phrase in the other index files. (The virtue of this is that those files may then contain fixed length records, potentially allowing rapid direct access to particular records, even though phrases vary in length.) Phrase tokens (i.e. instances) are recorded in the file *file-phrase-stats.dat*, and each phrase record in *global-phrase-stats.dat* contains a field pointing to the first and last records pertaining to the phrase in *file-phrase-stats.dat*.

file-phrase-stats.dat consists of a sequence of record blocks, one block per indexed file, which record the phrase tokens that occur in each file. After indexing, it is possible to ascertain which phrases a file contains simply by reading its block of records in *file-phrase-stats.dat*. Where a particular file's record block sits in the file can be readily determined because the start and end offsets of each file's block are recorded in *files.dat* (and in *corpus.dat*). Note that there is only one record per phrase in each file's block of records in *file-phrase-stats.dat*. A field of the phrase record stores the number of occurrences of each phrase in the file. It is possible to skip from file to file in relation to a specific phrase because phrase records contains a 'next record' field that gives the offset of the next record for the phrase to which the current record relates.

If a phrase has not been indexed before, a record is created for it in *global-phrase-stats.dat*. The record includes its unique ID and fields in which are stored the number of times the phrase occurs across all files, the number of files it occurs in, and the positions (byte offsets) of the first and last records for the phrase in the file *file-phrase-stats.dat*. If the phrase has been indexed before, its record in *global-phrase-stats.dat* is updated to reflect the number of occurrences encountered in the corpus so far.

As the indexer iterates through the corpus of files, it writes records to *corpus.dat* which store the word count of each file as well as each file's start and end offsets in *file-phrase-stats.dat*. (This duplicates some of the information in *files.dat*.) The total corpus word count is also stored.

Database loading

To create the full-text search index, data from the phrase index files is uploaded into a suitably defined and configured relational database. PostgreSQL was used for the present work. The three main tables store the index terms themselves, information about the indexed content items, and term/content item links respectively; their structures are set out in **Appendix B**.

A set of Python scripts reads data from the phrase index files and populates the `terms`, `content_items` and `term_links` tables of the database. The `psycopg2` library² is used by the scripts to connect to PostgreSQL and execute the relevant database INSERTs.

Database queries and results handling

The goal was to create a system that could support reasonably complex search queries, entered via a suitable client application. For prototyping and testing purposes a Windows GUI application was developed using Lazarus³. In real-world scenarios this would doubtless be replaced by a web client. The Windows search client presents the user with two edit boxes, one for terms to be ANDed (marked 'Text contains ALL these terms') and another for terms that are ORed (marked 'Text contains ONE OR MORE of these terms') – where 'term' here means a word or a phrase (between which the phrase index does not distinguish). This is a little like a much-reduced version of the Google advanced search UI⁴, with similar designs being seen elsewhere⁵. (See **Figure 1**.) An 'Exact term matching' checkbox allows the user to choose between exact and looser matching of query terms.

Figure 1: Hybrid SQL search prototype client

² <https://pypi.org/project/psycopg2/>

³ <https://www.lazarus-ide.org/>

⁴ https://www.google.co.uk/advanced_search

⁵ e.g. <https://link.springer.com/advanced-search>

A separate SQL query is executed on the basis of the contents of each edit box, and the results sets from these two queries are then ANDed. There is no limit on the number of comma-separated terms that may be entered into the two edit boxes.

The same form of query is used for both edit boxes. By way of example, if the user were to enter the terms 'apple' and 'microsoft' into the first edit box, and uncheck the 'Exact term matching' checkbox, the following query would be executed:

```
SELECT fid, tcsum, qterm FROM (
SELECT content_items.idx_fid AS fid, SUM(term_links.term_count) AS
tcsum, 'apple' AS qterm FROM content_items, term_links, terms
WHERE term_links.link_term_id = terms.term_id AND
content_items.idx_fid = term_links.content_fid AND term ILIKE
'%apple%' GROUP BY fid
UNION ALL
SELECT content_items.idx_fid AS fid, SUM(term_links.term_count) AS
tcsum, 'microsoft' AS qterm FROM content_items, term_links, terms
WHERE term_links.link_term_id = terms.term_id AND
content_items.idx_fid = term_links.content_fid AND term ILIKE
'%microsoft%' GROUP BY fid
) AS foo ORDER BY fid;
```

This example illustrates the fact that a separate SELECT exists for each query term entered by the user, the successive SELECTs then being concatenated with UNION ALL. Having a modular structure based on one SELECT per term makes the query extendable indefinitely, and means that it can be constructed programmatically.

Results come back to the client application in the following form:

fid	tcsum	qterm
11	1	apple
15	6	apple
17	37	apple
17	1	microsoft
18	3	microsoft
21	2	apple
22	17	apple
22	3	microsoft
23	2	microsoft
23	146	apple
24	27	apple
25	8	apple
27	6	apple
(etc.)		

The first column contains the file identifiers, the second column contains the number of matches, while the third contains a proxy for the matching term. The query independently aggregates the results for all the terms in each content item that match the ILIKE specifications, here '%apple%' and '%microsoft%'. That is to say, a search using prefix and suffix wildcards is performed. '%microsoft%', for example, would match 'microsoft sql server', 'using microsoft excel', etc. With exact term matching enabled (via the eponymous checkbox) the ILIKE expression is replaced by a simple equivalence test, which considerably speeds up query execution.

The search client must process the raw results set pertaining to the first edit box ('Text contains ALL these terms') to carry out the requisite Boolean ANDing of the query terms. This is not difficult: if a file ID (fid) occurs in the results just as many times as there are query terms, we

know that the corresponding content item contains all the query terms. Thus in the ‘apple’ + ‘microsoft’ example shown above, the content items with file ID (fid) values of 17, 22 and 23 are matches since each of those fid values occurs twice in the results, and there are two query terms. Handling the results that relate to the second edit box (‘Text contains ONE OR MORE of these terms’) is more straightforward: since we wish to OR them, all file IDs in the results set represent query matches.

To combine the results sets generated by the two queries relating to the edit boxes, the client application must perform another ANDing operation, by determining the intersection of the file IDs in the two processed results sets and generating a suitable combination of the `tcsum` scores.

Search performance against a test index database, derived from the 3051 chapters of 185 books on computing and tech, is very respectable. (The `terms` table in this case contains 1,732,952 rows, the `term_links` table 5,202,325 rows. The original index was created by running the indexing scripts with a four-word limit set for phrase length.) With index database and search client running locally on a mid-spec Windows laptop, with exact term matching enabled and with three or four terms entered into each edit box, typical query execution times are of the order of 30–300 milliseconds, and most commonly towards the lower end of that range.⁶

3. Discussion

By this point the reader may be thinking ‘well this is all very lovely, but why not store your content in the SQL database and use the database’s native full-text search capability?’. The question is pertinent, but equally of course it is a fact of life that use cases vary considerably. For some purposes it may simply make more sense to store content files on the filesystem, or on the Cloud in S3 buckets. And being able to do that, but still index your content and make it searchable in the manner you want, and in ways over which you have full control, is a seductive possibility. It’s good to have options.

Also worth noting is that the approach to indexing described here, indexing phrases rather than just single words, brings some significant benefits. In STEM subjects in particular, many (most?) of the objects and concepts of interest to information seekers are denoted using compound terms, i.e. phrases. Examples that spring to mind include the names of molecules and biomolecules (citrate synthase, carbon dioxide, cytochrome c, etc.), names of biochemical processes (protein folding, nitrogen fixation, Krebs Cycle, etc.), or scientific ideas (general relativity, dark matter, electromagnetic radiation, etc.). The same is true in computing and tech, the domain in which these investigations were carried out (SQL Server, Xamarin Forms, machine learning, feature engineering, ...). When we recognize this, there seems something distinctly second-rate about approaches to search that fail to treat multi-word terms as first class denizens of the referential world. And many search engines, or at any rate many of their implementations, do seem poor in this regard. Confronted by a query phrase, the first step often seems to be to break the phrase apart into its constituent words, and look to match those independently. (And then hope that the scoring methodology will reward those occasions when the words happen to come together to form the phrase the user was actually interested in.) As often as not, the user gets back a whole lot more than they bargained for – yet that *more* is, in information retrieval terms, and more importantly in terms of value to the user, actually *less*.

⁶ These are total times taken by the database to execute the two queries (one per edit box), and exclude client-side results processing.

Maybe this points to a wider issue to do with the commercialization, or commercialism, of search. As some of the big and/or rising search players (mentioning no names) have sought to sell search into larger, more lucrative markets than the rarified academic realms where information retrieval started out, so search has become infected by the idea that if some is good, more is better. Over-inclusiveness, and the proliferation of results far beyond the terms of the original query, are seen as virtues, because they hold out the promise that if the user doesn't find what they're actually looking for, it might still be possible to sell them *something*. If you're selling biscuits or socks, well and good, but biomedical information?

The investigations reported here had their origins in work on phrase indexing, with the aim of discerning relationships amongst academic research articles. But as the well-known saying has it, to someone in possession of a hammer, everything looks like a nail. It is gratifying, therefore, to find that a phrase index developed for one application also has utility in relation to another, i.e. full-text search. Regarding the form of the index used here, however, there are several aspects that could perhaps be improved. As noted in [3], the indexes do not currently store term locations, e.g. as byte offsets. That makes hit highlighting in the results a potentially arduous undertaking. The index might say that term X occurs in content item Y, but to highlight X in Y would require scanning Y for X and rewriting Y with markup inserted to effect the highlighting. In addition, a phrase index, especially if it extends to recording four-word phrases, can become quite large rather quickly⁷. (Although perhaps the history of computing should teach us to be relaxed about such capacity considerations.)⁸

On the other hand, the form of phrase index described has properties and potentialities not fully exploited by full-text search, but possibly relevant to the development of other novel functionality. For example, this query uses term occurrence statistics to retrieve books where 'electron' and 'markdown' occur more frequently than 1.75 times their corpus frequency:

```
SELECT DISTINCT(isbn) FROM content_items, term_links, terms
WHERE term_links.link_term_id = terms.term_id AND
content_items.idx_fid = term_links.content_fid AND
term ILIKE 'electron' AND (term_links.term_count /
(term_links.corpus_count/terms.host_count) > 1.75)
INTERSECT
SELECT distinct(isbn) FROM content_items, term_links, terms
WHERE term_links.link_term_id = terms.term_id AND
content_items.idx_fid = term_links.content_fid AND
term ILIKE 'markdown' AND (term_links.term_count /
(term_links.corpus_count/terms.host_count) > 1.75);
```

Using the phrase occurrence statistics it is also possible to identify the most 'significant' terms within a content item, which opens up a variety of interesting possibilities.

But we digress. The overall method described here would work as well with a simple word index; the use of a phrase index of the form described is not fundamental to the hybrid SQL approach.

⁷ The more so because a search index must include phrases that occur only once in a content item, whereas when indexing to support file relationship inferencing phrases can be required to occur twice or more to be included in the index, yielding a significant size reduction.

⁸ If index size, and phrase numerosity, were issues, scope exists to reduce the fraction of multi-word phrases admitted into the index by the indexer, for example by filtering on the basis of parts of speech tagging and named entity recognition.

4. Conclusion

In classic fashion, the upshot must be that there remains scope for further research, for example around scalability and performance with larger content corpora and correspondingly larger indexes. It would be interesting too to experiment with different forms of SQL query. A balance must be struck between query complexity and the amount of results processing needed. Here a relatively complex query is used, which accomplishes enough to ensure that quite light client-side processing suffices. But would greater flexibility come from employing simpler but more numerous queries? There are many such points to consider. What the work reported here shows, however, is that given an indexing script and a SQL database, one has the raw materials needed to build an effective full-text search solution, where proven database technology provides substantial reassurance of resilience in the face of potentially high transaction volumes.

References

- [1] Rijsbergen, C.J. van (1979) *Information Retrieval*. Butterworth-Heinemann.
- [2] Baeza-Yates, R. and B. Ribeiro-Neto (1999) *Modern Information Retrieval*. Addison-Wesley.
- [3] Powell, A. (2020). Phrase indexing and the identification of related academic research content. *Cambridge Open Engage*. (<https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2020-7zd6k-v2>)

Appendix A: Index file formats

files.dat

File type: text

This file that stores the names of indexed files, along with their IDs and various other items of information. A record in *files.dat* is a line of text structured like so:

```
<file_id>:<filepath_and_filename>[<word_count>][<start_offset>][<end_offset>]
```

- the file's approximate word count is obtained by splitting the extracted text on spaces
- the start offset is the byte offset of the start of the file's phrase records in *file-phrase-stats.dat*
- the end offset is the byte offset of the end of the file's phrase records in *file-phrase-stats.dat*

global-phrase-stats.dat

File type: binary

Purpose: to capture important data relating to each phrase that occurs in the corpus

First 4 bytes: the id of the last phrase record in *phrases.idx*

Then a series of 20-byte records:

phr_id	4 bytes	phrase ID
phr_count	4 bytes	global phrase count (i.e. number of times the phrase occurs in the corpus)
host_count	4 bytes	number of files containing the phrase
first_freq_offset	4 bytes	position of the first record in <i>file-phrase-stats.dat</i> relating to the phrase
last_freq_offset	4 bytes	position of the last record in <i>file-phrase-stats.dat</i> relating to the phrase

file-phrase-stats.dat

File type: binary

Purpose: to relate phrases to files

A series of 20-byte records:

file_id	4 bytes	ID of the file to which the record relates
phr_id	4 bytes	phrase ID
is_first_mention	4 bytes	0 if there's an earlier record in the file relating to the phrase; 1 if this is the first occurrence
file_count	4 bytes	number of times the phrase occurs in the file having ID = file_id
next_rec_offset	4 bytes	position in <i>file-phrase-stats.dat</i> of the next record relating to the phrase (NB this will be a mention in another file)

phrases.idx

File type: binary

Purpose: to store the phrase string, and associate it with an ID value

A series of variable-length records:

phr_id	4 bytes	phrase ID used during indexing
phr_length	4 bytes	the length of the phrase
phrase	variable	the phrase string (UTF-8 encoded)

corpus.dat

File type: binary

Purpose: to capture important data relating to the indexed corpus

First 4 bytes: the global (corpus) word count

Then a series of 16-byte records relating to the files making up the corpus:

idx	4 bytes	file ID
word_count	4 bytes	file word count
start_offset	4 bytes	offset of file's first record in <i>file-phrase-stats.dat</i>
end_offset	4 bytes	offset of file's last record in <i>file-phrase-stats.dat</i>

Appendix B: Database table structures

terms

term_id	int	[primary key]
term_word_count	int	no. of words in the term
term_char_count	int	no. of characters in the term
term	varchar(60)	an indexed word or phrase [indexed column]
corpus_count	int	no. of times term occurs in corpus
host_count	int	no. of files in corpus that contain term

content_items

item_type_id	int	for future use
pub_year	int	for future use
word_count	int	word count of content item
idx_fid	int	unique ID [primary key]
content_id	varchar(25)	descriptive ID
isbn	char(13)	ISBN of parent content item

term_links

id	int	[primary key]
content_fid	int	[FK -> content_items.idx_fid]
link_term_id	int	[FK -> terms.term_id]
term_count	int	no. of times the term occurs in the content item